

RESEARCH ARTICLE

TOWARD HELPING CHILDREN COPE WITH STRESS

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ABSTRACT

Stress is a response to any situation or factor that creates a negative emotional or physical change or both. People of all ages can experience stress. In small quantities, stress is good -- it can motivate you and help you be more productive. However, excessive stress can interfere with life, activities, and health. Stress can affect the way people think, act, and feel. Children learn how to respond to stress by what they have seen and experienced in the past. Most stresses experienced by children may seem insignificant to adults. But because children have few previous experiences from which to learn, even situations that require small changes can have an enormous impact on a child's feelings of safety and security. This paper examines how children experience different stressful events, their ways of reacting and coping with these stressors. It also offers parent or care givers tips on how to assist children in understanding and using effective adaptation and coping strategies to relieve stress.

Keywords: Children, Stress, Reaction, Cope, Change, Motivation

Received for Publication: 18/09/15

Accepted for Publication: 20/12/15

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INTRODUCTION

Stress is the body's physical, chemical, and emotional reaction to an overwhelming, confusing, or exciting situation. Children of all ages can experience stress, but how they respond and cope with it depends on factors such as age, temperament, and family environment. Stress is an inevitable component of human life, so reaction to stress is a central feature of human development. Psychologists view stress as a process involving the recognition of and response to dangers (Fleming, Baum, & Singer, 1984). When people think and talk about stress, they usually focus on its negative consequences, that is, a stomach ache, a tension headache, a tight throat, an aching back, a short temper, crying jags, dizzy spells, sleepless nights, asthma attacks, and countless other unpleasant outcomes.

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However, without some levels of stress, life would be boring and purposeless. Stress is beneficial if it contributes to personal growth and increases people's confidence and skills for dealing with future events (Goodhart, 1985). This is also truism of children. As suggested by the Chinese, stress is composed of two characters: one meaning danger and the other opportunity. Danger and opportunity are not so opposites of two sides of a single coin.

Coping behaviours are central to stress. Coping involves the responses people make in order to master, tolerate or reduce stress (Fleming, Baum & Singer, 1984; Lazarus & De Longis, 1983). There are two basic types of coping. Folkman and Lazarus (1985) identify them as problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies.

Lacking specific information on how children react to stress, professionals and social workers have often drawn inferences from the adult literature. But as psychologists have come to recognize that children are not miniature adults and since emotional disorders in childhood do not fit easily into categories of emotional illness in adults; and there is little continuity between emotional disorder in childhood and neurosis in adult life, they (Psychologists) have increasingly turned to the study of stress and coping among children. Furthermore, Psychologists are finding that popular notions are not always accurate. For instance, such events as hospitalization, birth of a sibling, divorce, or war are not necessarily or universally stressful. Children's perception of such events greatly influences their stress reactions. Many of the stressors long cited by clinical psychologists as extraordinarily stressful are actually experienced by children as less stressful than such events as being ridiculed, getting lost, or receiving a poor report card (Compas 1987).

In evaluating matters of stress and reaction to it, three factors stand out in the emerging body of research as important: (1) the characteristics of the child, (2) developmental factors, and (3) situation-specific actors (Altshuler & Ruble, 1989; Band & Weisz, 1988; Compas, 1987). An examination of each of these factors at this stage is pertinent.

Dispositional and temperamental differences among children play a central role in influencing their coping resources (Kagan, 1983). Children differ in their sensitivity to the environment, with some showing signs of arousal and distress to a much wider array of events than others. So they must cope with a great number of stressful situations than do more stress – resistant children. Moreover, children differ in the way they react once they are aroused or threatened. For example, whereas some become aggressive and enraged, others become withdrawn and sullen and still others resort to daydreaming, fantasizing and escapist behaviours.

Developmental factors also play a part. For instance, 3 to 4 year old are distinguished from older youngsters by their difficulty in comprehending the finality of death. Similarly, children's emerging sense of self in childhood makes them more vulnerable to events that threaten their self-esteem than they were to these same events in an earlier period. Additionally, cognitive

problem-solving skills differ as a function of age; as children gets older, their ability to devise strategies for coping with stress expands, and they become more playful (Maccoby, 1983).

Situation factors influence how children experience and deal with stress. Parents mediate many of the effects of stressful crises. A caregiver's irritability, anxiety, self-doubt and feeling of incompetence are likely to intensify a child's fear of hospitalization. On the other hand, support from the family can have a steeling effect, buffering the influence of stressors (Garmezy, 1983; Rutter, 1981). Children's self-esteem is strengthened when they know that they are accepted by their parents and others despite their difficulties or faults. And resourceful caregivers can help children to define and understand their problems and find ways for dealing with them (Dubow & Tisak, 1989).

The present study examined different ways by which children react to stress. Nine different stressful events which children may experience in the course of development, and how they cope with each of these stressors, are highlighted in turn.

Child Abuse and Neglect

Abuse is a non-accidental physical attack on or injury to children by individuals caring for them. Neglect is defined as the absence of adequate social, emotional and physical care (Vander Zanden, 1993). Both physically abused and emotionally deprived children typically have low self-esteem, poor self-control, and negative feelings about the world. However, whereas physically abused children tend to show high levels of rage, frustration, and aggression; those reared by emotionally unavailable parents tend to be withdrawn and dependent and to exhibit more severe mental and behavioural damage as they become older (England, Jacobvitz, & Sroufe, 1988).

Maltreated children (abused and neglected children) typically react in a varied number of ways, these include:

As infants, they may not thrive, and they may lag in motor, social, and language development. As preschoolers, they may display a lack of "basic trust", "frozen watchfulness", and anxious and compliant behaviour among adults. As school-aged children, they may internalize the feeling that they are responsible for family problems and perform poorly on academic tasks.

Maltreated adolescents may show marked depression, rebelliousness, anger, truancy, and antisocial behaviours (Klimes-Dougan & Kistner, 1990). Being neglected or abused as a child increases an individual's risk for delinquency, adult criminal behaviour, and violent criminal behaviour (Olwens, 1980). Furthermore, maltreated children, most often, grow up to become abusive or neglecting parents.

Exposure to Violence

Although there are very serious implications of the effects of exposure to violence on children and families, Psychologists are just beginning to glimpse the magnitude of the problem. Exposure to community violence is defined as frequent and continual exposure to the use of

guns, knives, drugs, and random violence (Osofsky, 1999). In Nigeria, to say that children are excessively being exposed to violence is understating the obvious: armed robbery (even in broad daylight), overt display of aggression, communal clashes, ethnic militancy, insurgency, terrorism and so on.

Researchers have shown that children who have been exposed to violence react in many ways, these include: School-age children often experience increases in anxiety and sleep disturbances. Both school-age children and pre-schoolers exposed to violence are less likely to explore their physical environment and play freely, showing less motivation to master their environment (Pynoos, 1996). Autonomous striving may be subverted by trauma-related avoidance behaviour; on the other hand, autonomous striving may be accelerated by trauma-generated adventure some pursuits (possibly beyond the child's developmental capabilities) (Pynoos, 1996). Regression in developmental achievements, such as toileting and language, is common (Drell et al., 1998).

Development of aggressive behaviours and negative emotions may influence the pre-school task of differentiating affective states" and the capacity for school-age children to elaborate on their affective expressions (Pynoos, 1996), and attachment problems, characterized by avoidance, resistance, apprehension, aggression, apathy, freezing, and stilling (Main & Solomon, 1999).

Divorce

Though researchers have found that the quality of the child's relationship with both parents is the predictor of his or her post-divorce adjustment (children who maintain stable, loving relationships with both parents appear to experience fewer emotional scars: they exhibit less stress and less aggressive behaviour, and their school performance and peer relations are better than those of children lacking such relationships (Lingem Peel & Repucci, 1982; Seltzer, 1991), three clusters of adjustment patterns have been found among youngsters from divorced or remarried families Hetherington (1989):

Aggressive, Insecure Children: prone to both impulsive, irritable outbursts and to sullen brooding periods of withdrawal at home and at school. They experience low levels of self-esteem, had few areas or satisfaction, were unpopular with their peers, had difficulties in school - all contributing to their lonely, unhappy, angry anxious, and insecure childhoods.

Opportunistic-Competent Children: seemed to adapt well, were high in self-esteem, gave little evidence of problem behaviour, were popular with peers and teachers, and functioned reasonably well in the classroom. They were however found to be manipulative, attempting to ingratiate themselves with people in power.

Caring-Competent Children: they exhibited same adaptive responses as opportunistic-competent children except that they were much less inclined toward manipulative behaviours and were disposed toward helping and sharing behaviours, often befriending neglected or rejected peers. Other studies show however that much depends on the age of children at the time of divorce. For

instance, Walterstein & Kelly (1980) found that: Pre-schoolers often responded to their parents' divorce with pervasive feelings of sadness, strong wishes for reconciliation, and worries about having to take care of themselves. They also experienced feelings of rejection, and guilt for having caused the break-up. Older children and adolescents were better able to accurately assign responsibility for the divorce (and so not blame themselves), to resolve loyalty conflicts, and to assess and to cope with the transitions accompanying family dissolution.

Troubled Parent(S)

Parenting, like other aspects of human functioning, is influenced by the relatively enduring characteristics, or personality, of a man or woman (Belsky, 1990). So, the personality and psychological wellbeing of the parent is a strong determinant of parental functioning. Studies have shown that troubled parents are more likely to have troubled children. A six year study of 693 families by Parker (1987) found that 66% of children with emotionally troubled mothers had psychological problems; 47% had problems in families where only the father had symptoms; and 72% had problems when both parents were disturbed (double the rate for children with two healthy parents).

Parental Death

Theoretically, environmental threats can stimulate withdrawal, freezing, or escape behaviour. In a well-functioning goal-directed partnership between child and parent, such escape usually entails escaping to an attachment figure. Loss of parent can therefore lead to disturbance. Suffice to say, however, that, the loss of parent(s) does not necessarily predispose a child to psychopathology if there is a foster parent or substitute parent(s) who care and provide love, emotional support, food, and other necessary things for the child. In the absence of the parent(s) or an adequate foster parent(s), the child may respond by being dismissive as a result, habitually deny or dismiss environmental threats. They may therefore have a higher threshold for experiencing negative emotion or perceiving attachment needs, and thus exhibit what Bowlby called "compulsive self-reliance".

Child's Illness

For sick children whose illnesses or disabilities would require operation and hospitalization leading to their being separated from the adult on whom they mainly depend, they become anxious to some degree. If the separation is of a longer duration, the child's uneasiness mounts and certain patterns of reaction occur. Bowlby demonstrated these patterns rather clearly in two-year-olds who were hospitalized. He delineated a continuum of three phases occurring in a sequence. (1) protest, (2) despair, and (3) detachment. The phase of protest is the familiar reaction usually called "separation anxiety". The child takes all the steps open to him to bring about his mother's return. The child cries loudly, searches, and cooperates. This phase usually lasts a day or two. If the mother does not return, the phase of despair sets in. In this phase, the need and longing for mother is as great as ever, but the hope of her returning is fading, and the child's noisy demands for her ceases. The protest is replaced by apathy and withdrawal, but the child's thought and behaviour are still directed toward the lost mother. This phase lasts roughly

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three weeks. If an adequate mother substitute takes over in this, time, the infant responds by relating to the new mother and recovers. Through this phase, the trauma is mild enough that the child can recover without serious residual effect.

If no such single figure is available and too many substitutes are offered, children turn inward instead of toward people. Their withdrawal becomes more complete as they use more and more autocratic and narcissistic personality defences. At this point recovery will not be without residual emotional scarring. The child would manifest disturbances of feeding such as marasmus in which he may stop eating, become cachectic, and die if this emotional need is completely unmet.

Observation of depressive reactions in infants and young children has led to provisions in hospitals for "rooming in" and for more frequent visiting of the young hospitalized child. These observations have stirred child-care agencies, with the result that now, when infants and young children have to separate from their mothers, adequate plans for mother substitutes are made more regularly.

High Parental Standard

When children perceive parental standards as too extremist, the child could react by refusing to learn to share and cooperate in social situations. Aggressive insistence by a child on his own pleasure will not be tolerated well by his peer groups and eventually will lead to fights and isolation. This coping style will interfere with socializing experiences with peers and adults, just as surely as will failure to master any other crucial developmental task.

Inadequate Parental Attention

The prevalence of psychological disorder among children are related to several factors, which has been highlighted by Rutter's (1978, 1989) family adversity index. They include six family predictors of behaviour problems among children of which low income/SES, and parental antisocial behaviour or parental-inattention are highlighted. Theorists assert that extreme parental neglect or inadequate attention deprives the child of the opportunity to form a selective attachment. This can cause reactive attachment disorder also known as analectic depression.

Such variations in the quality of early attachments are also associated with children's response to stress or emotional difficulties. A child with an anxious attachment has formed a selective attachment, but the attachment figure responds inadequately and inconsistently to the child's needs. As a result, the infant/child experiences anxiety about exploration and ambivalence about the attachment figure (Ainsworth et al., 1978). Thus, they over-react to situations that their peers take in their stride e.g. school tests or mother leaving home for the day, change of school or going to the hospital. Children with such attachment (anxious) have lower self-esteem, and they are less competent and more dependent on others (Cassidy, 1988; Sroufe & Fleeson, 1986).

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The coercion concept by Patterson suggests that when unwilling, parents positively reinforce children's misbehaviour giving to their demands. This underscores parental discipline, and it is often the practice of neglectful parents. They show no concern for their children's emotional needs or their need for discipline. Researches have shown that children sometimes misbehave, a way of getting attention rather than as a way of getting what they want (Negative attention). Social learning theorists have suggested that negative attention concept should be understood properly because many children may be reinforced by negative attention since they are not getting attention – enough love – in other ways.

Social Economics Status

A number of social and societal factors also play a role in how children react to stress. More psychological problems are found among children who grow up in poor inner city neighbourhoods. Professionals who wish to promote children's mental health therefore need to be concerned about poverty which triggers other factors like inadequate schooling and violence.

The socio-economic status of the parents affects the child directly. This influences the child in forming peer group that might be destructive. Such peer group can teach antisocial behaviour as is evident in inner-city gangs/touts. Some children do not have opportunity to go to school and thus used as contributor to maintaining the family by selling in the market/hawking on the highways. These have various implications for the child's adjustment to societal laws in that the child does not respect laws because no authority figure has been found in parents. In fact, researchers have suggested socialized delinquency, in which criminal acts occur in company of others met on the streets, cross-cultural evidence also points to broad societal influence on externalizing behaviour. Violence has become a major concern all over the world. The age ranges of 12-19 years have been arrested for various criminal charges and the rate of death by homicide among 15 and 24-year old males in the United States and other countries even Nigeria. The problem of poverty is easily identified in western world because of the fact that young black men are far more likely to be murdered than young white men which also points to the problem created by poverty, social disadvantages and limited opportunities.

Guidelines for Helping Children Coping with Stress

Assisting children in understanding and using effective adaptation and coping strategies must be based on the child's developmental level and understanding of the nature of the stress-inducing event. Teachers and parents can prevent and reduce stress for children in many ways:

* Help the child anticipate stressful events, such as a first haircut or the birth of a sibling. Adults can prepare children by increasing their understanding of the upcoming event and reducing its stressful impact (Marion, 2003). Over-preparing children for upcoming stressful events, however, can prove even more stressful than the event itself (Donate-Bartfield & Passman, 2000). Adults can judge the optimal level of preparation by encouraging the child to ask questions if he or she wants to know more.

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- * Provide supportive environments where children can play out or use art materials to express their concerns (Gross & Clemens, 2002).
- * Help children identify a variety of coping strategies (e.g., "ask for help if someone is teasing you"; "tell them you don't like it"; "walk away"). Coping strategies help children feel more effective in stressful situations (Fallin, Wallinga, & Coleman, 2001).
- * Help children recognize, name, accept, and express their feelings appropriately.
- * Teach children relaxation techniques. Consider suggesting to a child such things as "take three deep breaths"; "count backwards"; "tense and release your muscles"; "play with play dough"; "dance"; "imagine a favorite place to be and visit that place in your mind" (use creative imagery) (O'Neill, 1993).
- * Practice positive self-talk skills (e.g., "I'll try. I think I can do this.") to help in promoting stress management (O'Neill, 1993).

Other basic strategies include implementing sound positive discipline strategies, following consistent routines, enhancing cooperation, and providing time for children to safely disclose their concerns and stresses privately and in groups. Our increasing knowledge about the importance and impact of stress on young children should be put to good use in reducing stress factors for young children and in assisting children to increase coping strategies and healthy responses to the unavoidable stresses in their lives.

CONCLUSION

The narrative above leads to the conclusion that the stress is ubiquitous, and very common among adults and children. The factors that can predispose children to stress are highlighted, and some guidelines that can ameliorate stress level among children are also itemized. The paper will be useful for developing adequate self-awareness among children students and also to develop effective techniques to deal with stress. Children would certainly benefit if they get adequate family support.

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